

D2.2 - SCENT Research Report on citizen attitudes and behaviours

Smart Toolbox for Engaging Citizens into a People-Centric Observation Web

Abstract

Whilst citizen participation in environmental policy making is still in its infancy, there are signs of a growing level of interest. The majority of citizens, though, both as individuals and as groups often feel disengaged from influencing environmental policies. They also remain unaware of publicly available information, such as the GEOSS or Copernicus initiatives. The SCENT project will alleviate this barrier. It will enable citizens to become the ‘eyes’ of the policy makers by monitoring land-cover/use changes in their everyday activities. This is done through a constellation of smart collaborative technologies delivered by the SCENT toolbox in TRLs 6-8.

The purpose of this deliverable is to establish the current attitudes and behaviours of citizens in relation to their participation in environmental monitoring. The research focuses on the two large scale pilots – the urban case of Kifisos and the rural case of the Danube Delta. A combined qualitative and quantitative approach was used to assess the attitudes and behaviours, and understand their potential involvement in SCENT.

Keywords: focus groups, desk research, online survey, attitudes and behaviours, citizen observatory.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CO	Citizen observatories
COP21	2015 Paris Climate Conference
EO	Earth observations
EU	European Union
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

Table 1: List of Abbreviations

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides evidence of advances towards the achievement of project objectives to investigate the current behaviour of citizens in relation to land resource management issues and how they can be motivated to become involved in SCENT environmental monitoring activities.

Citizens are concerned about the impact that climate change is having. In the Danube Delta, Romania and along the Kifisos River, Attica region, Greece, citizens have experienced first-hand the effects of climate change and human intervention which has impacted flooding in the respective areas. As part of this research report, desk research was conducted of publicly available information into attitudes and behaviours of citizens in the EU in general, and particularly in Greece and Romania, an online survey was distributed amongst citizens in Greece, Romania, the UK and Ireland and focus groups were conducted in Romania and Greece to add further understanding.

The Danube Delta is one of the largest wetlands in Europe, viewed as a “source of life” for many, as it provides economic activities for residents and hosts a diverse range of habitats and life forms. However, human interventions such as canalisation and agriculture have negatively impacted upon the delta, which within the context of climate change have led to increased frequency of extreme hydrological events. For citizens, local to the Kifisos river, it has been suggested that people only remember it exists when it is raining and causes problems such as flooding businesses and homes. Many would trace the increase in flood events along the Kifisos to deforestation in the mountains above Athens, and inappropriate building along the river bank.

Regarding motivating citizens to get involved in SCENT, some important factors were uncovered, such as, guilt, personal and social norms, and a sense of environmental citizenship. Feedback was regularly highlighted as an important feature of maintaining citizen engagement in such projects and suggestions of activities that SCENT could easily be incorporate into were given.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The aim of this report is to establish current attitudes and behaviours of citizens in relation to land resource management issues, and their participation in environmental monitoring. This report is for the completion of Task 2.2 of SCENT and will contribute to the development of pilot studies for WP2 of SCENT. These pilot studies will take place in Romania and Greece, therefore information from these countries is given a particular focus.

This report uses three distinctive types of research. Firstly, publicly available desk research, such as the Eurobarometer, and information given by existing partner networks throughout the European Union (EU). Information relating to citizen attitudes towards climate change and various environmental objectives of the EU were widely available, however information relating to attitudes towards land resource management issues and participation in environmental monitoring were difficult to attain limiting the strength of conclusions in this aspect report. Further details of the desk research undertaken are given in chapter 2.

Secondly, data from an online survey, conducted in conjunction with Task 1.1, was collected from citizens in the Attica region and Danube Delta to elicit current attitudes and behaviours towards the environment and land use, in particular flooding. Chapter 3 will discuss this in more detail.

Thirdly, focus groups were held in the Attica region and Danube Delta with citizens where attitudes and behaviours in relation to the environment in general, flooding, and general views of the SCENT project were explored. Further details of this component of research are given in chapter 4.

At present, there are various projects being run under the H2020 remit that investigate and create “citizen observatories” such as Grow, Ground Truth 2.0 and LandSense. This sort of citizen involvement in environmental monitoring is a relatively new concept, therefore it is possible that more pertinent information will be available in the future. Citizen observatories seek to engage citizens in monitoring the environment and providing valuable real-time information to promote environmental governance and decision making.

The key objective of WP2 that this research report fulfils is:

- To investigate the current behaviour of citizens in relation to land resource management issues and how they can be motivated to become involved in SCENT environmental monitoring activities.

1.2 Intended readership

This document, the “D2.2 Research Report on citizen attitudes and behaviours”, provides information about WP2 Incentivising citizen participation in SCENT and the methods used to establish the current attitudes and behaviours of citizens in relation to their participation in environmental monitoring. This was completed during a six month period, nominally scheduled from September 2016 to February 2017. The information contained in this report in particular considers the SCENT Toolbox being applied for floods.

The intended readership is those partners in the consortium who are involved in designing appropriate and high impact incentives in the project. This research report may also be of interest for other research projects investigating COs and citizens’ attitudes and behaviours towards the environment.

1.3 Inputs from other projects

Work conducted by previous European Union Framework Programmes, namely COBWEB, Citi-Sense and WeSenseIt, was consulted and where appropriate referred to. The work previously conducted, particularly in the area of citizen observatories, has been highly pertinent in understanding what incentivises citizen participation in such projects which is discussed further in section 2.

1.4 Relation with other SCENT deliverables

This deliverable presents work conducted as part of Task 2.2 which combined qualitative and quantitative methods to record and assess attitudes and behaviours of local citizens regarding how they can be involved in SCENT.

The online survey component presented in this deliverable was conducted in conjunction with Task 1.1 Definition of the end user and stakeholder needs relevant to citizen observatories. Further details of the activities undertaken as part of this task are presented in Deliverable 1.1 SCENT Stakeholder analysis & End-user needs and requirements. This document will also be influential in the large-scale demonstrations to be held in the Danube Delta, Romania and Attica region, Greece, the details of these will be presented in Deliverables 7.2 and 7.3.

2 Desk research

This chapter will outline the desk research conducted as part of Task 2.2. The chapter is structured to explore wider issues of climate change and the environment in section 1. The attitudes of citizens in the pilot countries of Romania and Greece towards the environment and climate change are then explored in section 2, which focuses in particular on the attitudes and behaviours of citizens in relation to land resource management issues, such as flooding. Section 3 investigates participation in environmental monitoring, with a particular focus on citizens' observatories. Details of other European Union projects are given, in particular any lessons that can be learned from them and applied in the SCENT project.

2.1 Climate change/Environmental issues

The issue of climate change is often thought of as “one of the greatest challenges of the modern age” (European Commission, 2014a, p. 2) and the prevention of climate change is one of the European Union's (EU) main priorities. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) was formed in 1994 and defined key principles for the international effort to combat climate change. Whilst principles such as industrialised countries taking responsibility for global greenhouse gas emissions were agreed to, no commitments were given (European Commission, 2014a). Various protocols and action plans have since been drafted in a global bid to tackle climate change.

Extreme weather events which can lead to flooding are expected to increase over the coming years, and there has already been a 60% increase in such events over the last thirty years (Climate News Network, 2016).

2.1.1 UN Objectives

The Kyoto Protocol (effective 2005) and Doha Amendment (effective 2012) by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) were viewed as important steps in tackling the issue of global warming as they brought about “binding quantifiable objectives for limiting and reducing greenhouse gas emissions” (European Commission, 2014a, p. 2). In addition, the Durban Platform for Enhanced Action (2010) brought about an EU commitment to cutting emissions 20% below the 1990 levels (European Commission, 2014a). More recently in 2015, COP21 was held and led to what has been termed the “Paris Agreement”. The key points of this agreement are “to keep global temperature increases “well-below” 2°C and to pursue efforts to limit it to 1.5°C; to peak greenhouse gas emissions as soon as possible and achieve balance between sources and sinks of greenhouse gases in the second half of this century; to review progress every five years” (BBC News, 2016). In addition, it has brought about new requirements such as strengthening knowledge on the climate such as research, systematic observation and warning systems which will inform decision making and climate services (Berger and Ollier, 2016).

2.1.2 EU Objectives

The EU can play an important role in shaping the climate change agenda, with powers to act in most areas of environmental policy e.g. “air and water pollution, waste management and climate change” (European Parliament, 2016). Currently the EU is implementing the “Paris agreement” which has additionally brought about reforms to emissions trading, a new target to reduce greenhouse gas

emissions from the EU by no less than 40% by 2030, and new legislation targeting the promotion of renewable energy (European Parliament, 2016).

In March 2010, the European Commission set out its ten-year strategy to establish smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. Notably, climate change was one of the five headline targets which set out that by Europe 2020:

“Climate change and energy sustainability

- *greenhouse gas emissions 20% (or even 30%, if the conditions are right) lower than 1990*
- *20% of energy from renewables*
- *20% increase in energy efficiency”* (European Commission, 2010)

As such, it has become a major policy area for the EU. In March 2011, the European Commission extended its 2020 goals as it set out a cost-effective pathway to achieving its goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions with its “Roadmap to moving to a competitive low carbon economy in 2050”. Additionally, the EU Budget for the period 2014-2020 allocates a fifth of spending to climate related spending which is said to highlight “the importance Europe places on the fight against climate change and efforts to handle the climate crisis” (European Commission, 2014a, p. 2).

These targets are viewed as important by many European citizens and recognise the importance of national governments to also support these targets (European Commission, 2014a). 88% of European citizens believe Europe will be using more renewable energy by 2050; 87% expect we will be more energy efficient (European Commission, 2011a, p. 4). However, in recent years there has been a fall in the perceived realism of the objectives (European Commission, 2015).

2.2 Attitudes and behaviours

In order to engage citizens in environmental monitoring, as SCENT aims to do, it is important to understand the motivations for environmental engagement in the first place and citizens’ opinions of the environment in general. This chapter is organised to understand motivations for engaging with positive environmental behaviours, such as recycling waste, and European citizens’ attitudes towards climate change and the environment. As evidence suggests that climate change is leading to increased frequency and severity in extreme weather events (Owusu et al., 2015), understanding attitudes to climate change is important before moving on to establishing attitudes towards specific land management issues such as flooding. The chapter then focuses specifically on land use management issues, which SCENT seeks to assist in, with a particular focus on the pilot countries of Greece and Romania.

2.2.1 Environment/climate change

2.2.1a What motivates people to act in an environmentally friendly way?

Significant predictors of environmental behaviour have been suggested by (Pensini et al., 2012) as inclination to act collectively; personal and social norms; belief of control over environment and self-efficacy; feelings of guilt (individually and/or collectively); desire to increase one’s moral standing; and sense of identification with one’s country. Individuals who show a high openness to change, altruism and closeness to nature are more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviour (Barr, 2007). Intrinsic motivation is also an important predictor of pro-environmental behaviours such as “feeling

good about recycling” and is more likely to encourage the continuation of pro-environmental behaviours (De Young, 1986) than when extrinsic motivators, such as monetary reward, are used. Response efficacy, the belief that an individual’s actions make a difference to a problem, is another important motivator of pro-environmental behaviours (Roberts, 1996), and that “an awareness of need, an awareness that related actions can alleviate the problem and an ascription of responsibility to the self to act” can increase appropriate behaviours (Barr, 2007, p. 440).

Personal experience also plays an important role in pro-environmental behaviour, which is likened to a “behavioural snowball effect” (Barr, 2007, p. 439) as well as how one perceives the relationship between humans and the environment. Environmental citizenship is highlighted by (Barr, 2007) as an important psychological factor influencing environmental behaviour, which incorporates “a balance between rights and responsibilities, an active involvement within society, characterised by a feeling of good community spirit and a part of the local decision making processes regarding the environment” (p.442). This sentiment is echoed by the work of (Davies et al., 2005) who wrote that “good relationships between communities, local authorities and manufacturers were seen as pivotal in establishing collaborative action” (p.8) and individuals having a wider societal duty to care for the environment. The behaviour of others also plays a key role in shaping pro-environmental behaviour and will likely be modified when people are made aware of social norms and accept the norm (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), particularly in the realm of recycling behaviour. Again, this theme of norms is reflected by (Davies et al., 2005) who suggest that if behavioural norms were to be upgraded, people will still feel an expectation that they should adhere to it.

2.2.1b Whole EU

With the specific attributes of what motivates environmentally friendly behaviour in mind, it is important to consider what people understand as being “the environment”. In a study conducted by the European Commission, respondents identified issues such as “the protection of nature, the state of the environment for the next generation, pollution in towns and cities, manmade disasters and climate” (2011b, p. 7) as closely related to “the environment”. The environment is a concern for people within the EU as 50% of all Europeans think that climate change is one of the world’s most serious problems (European Commission, 2014a). However, there has been no change in attitudes over recent time relating to the environment (European Commission, 2014b). The issues citizens demonstrated concern over typically included: air and water pollution; waste generated; depleted resources; chemicals impacting health; and species lost to deforestation (European Commission, 2014b).

In regard to environmental protection, the self-efficacy can play an important role in determining environmental behaviours, as demonstrated in section 2.1.1a. 85% of citizens believe they can play a role in protecting the environment (European Commission, 2014b), which is important for developing techniques of engagement. 77% of survey respondents also indicated that problems relating to the environment have a direct impact on them (European Commission, 2014b, p. 17) and environmental protection is viewed as important in boosting economic growth which may be a strong motivator for engaging in pro-environmental behaviours. 50% of all Europeans report that they have taken some form of action in the past six months to tackle climate change but when prompted with specific actions they could have taken to tackle climate change, responses indicate 89% of respondents have taken action (European Commission, 2014a).

However, only 25% of Europeans consider they have a personal responsibility to fight climate change (European Commission, 2014a) and more feel that everyone should share responsibility for the environment (European Commission, 2011a). With regard to information about the environment, 8% of citizens across the EU feel very well informed about environmental issues, 54% fairly well informed (European Commission, 2014b, p. 36), but more information about environmental issues is desired (European Commission, 2011b). In addition, the main priorities from households with regard to protecting the environment are: sorting waste; reducing home energy consumption; using public transport (European Commission, 2014a). Whilst these priorities are good and impactful for negating the effects of climate change, there are greater ways in which citizens can be involved in protecting the environment.

In general, there is a belief that more needs to be done by citizens, industry and government alike to protect the environment (European Commission, 2014b, p. 64). Tackling climate change is viewed as the responsibility mainly of national governments, businesses and industry and the EU itself by citizens (European Commission, 2014b).

2.2.1c Greece and Romania

This section of the report will focus on data available from the pilot countries in the SCENT study, Romania and Greece. As the project will be piloted there, it is important to understand the attitudes of those countries' citizens towards the environment and any additional research that may indicate threats and opportunities to the project.

Protecting the environment is very important to the Greek people on a personal level (70%), 27% indicated it was fairly important (European Commission, 2014b). The Eurobarometer study would suggest that it is of less importance to Romanians, as 51% of citizens reported protecting the environment was very important (European Commission, 2014b). As to the role they can play in protecting the environment, 42% of Greeks totally agree that they can make a difference, 43% would tend to agree. In Romania 43% would totally agree that they can play a role, 39% tend to agree (European Commission, 2014b). 21% of citizens in Greece report that they have a personal responsibility for tackling climate change, 10% of Romanians feel they have the same personal responsibility. However, 47% report they have taken no action against climate change in Greece and this figure is 67% in Romania (European Commission, 2014a, p. 32).

Regarding information about environmental issues, 9% of Greeks and 10% of Romanians feel very well informed (European Commission, 2014b, p. 36). The main issues Greeks identify as lacking in information are: the impact of chemicals on health; water pollution; agricultural pollution; depletion of natural resources and invasive species. In Romania, the issues of concern are: air pollution, impact on health of chemicals, soil degradation, depletion of natural resources; and water pollution.

In terms of trusted sources of information, there is a significant difference between Greece and Romania in whom they trust. Romanians would tend to trust information regarding the environment from the TV most of all (61%) (European Commission, 2014b). In addition, Romanians tend to trust the European Union more than the EU average rating (Romania: 47%; EU: 33%) and have low trust in their national parliament (82% would tend not to trust it) (European Commission, 2016a). Romanians are the most enthusiastic citizens in the EU in terms of projections of the future, images and general attitudes towards the EU (Chiciudean and Corbu, 2015), only 14% describe their image of the EU as

negative (European Commission, 2016a). This bodes well for the efficacy of this project due to it being funded by the EU, however the involvement of government agencies could pose a hindrance to citizen engagement due to the lack of trust in these authorities. Greeks would tend not to trust the EU (82%) and have low trust in their national parliament (89%) (European Commission, 2016b). Information about the environment from scientists is perceived as most reliable (64%), followed by environmental protection associations (39%) and the internet (36%). The least reliable information is believed to come from companies, the national government and local government (European Commission, 2014b, p. 416).

2.2.2 Land resource management

2.2.2a Whole EU

Research into land resource management was particularly focused on the impacts of flooding as an issue that is important in the pilot regions. It is commonly believed that climate change is leading to an increase in the frequency and severity of extreme rainfall and other devastating weather events (Owusu et al., 2015). Approximately one third of all natural disasters are flood related (UNISDR, 2012) and two major contributing factors are climate change and increased urbanisation of river basins (Kay et al., 2011).

Within Europe, many changes to member state flood policies have been influenced by the EU Flood Directive. The Directive “applies to all kinds of floods (rivers, lakes, flash floods, urban floods, coastal floods including storm surges and tsunamis)” (European Commission, 2016c). The directive makes flood risk management a responsibility shared around relevant stakeholders at various designated levels (Owusu et al., 2015).

(Grothmann and Reusswig, 2008) write that communication to citizens in areas prone to flooding must be motivated by not just the risk and the consequences to their livelihood of flooding, but also the effectiveness and cost of precautionary measures. (Bradford et al., 2012) find that awareness of flood risks is correlated strongly with previous flood experiences, but long periods without any flood events can reduce awareness. As such, people may only be motivated to get involved if messages are communicated by experienced flood victims such as through personal accounts; they are given statements on risks they currently face; the information is communicated in the most salient way possible to impact those who have no direct experience of flood events; the information is tailored for the local area; and the measures that are suggested to prevent flooding can be implemented easily (Bradford et al., 2012).

2.2.2b Romania and Greece

In the Danube Delta, Romania, flooding is important for the whole ecosystem, water renewal in lakes and “insuring a normal evolution of both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems” (Armaş and Avram, 2009). However, this was somewhat disrupted by the “canalization, reclamation and water regulation” associated with communism (van Assche et al., 2012). In addition, human tensions have arisen between locals and authorities in the concerted effort to conserve the area (van Assche et al., 2012) and the creation of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reservation which created restrictions on hunting and fishing activities, an important source of economic activity for the region (Armaş and Avram, 2009). These restrictions have created feelings of discrimination for the locals, along with feelings of being stigmatised, disempowered and marginalised, negatively impacting on locals’ “environmental

perceptions and experiences” (van Assche et al., 2012). Further confounding this issue is the suspicion of bureaucrats, scientists and conservation literature brought about by “green talk” from authorities, but locals argue they have yet to see any action from these authorities (van Assche et al., 2012). Events organised to encourage environmental participation and sustainable development have been interpreted as “pro forma obligations to international actors” (van Assche et al., 2012). (Constant and Bell, 2016) wrote that “protected areas cannot be sustained without the support of local people,” which may pose a challenge to citizen engagement within the region. Whilst the flooding of the delta does pose a risk to the human communities of the region (such as the risk of material damage, psychological stress and human victims) (Armaş and Avram, 2009), the delta is a source of livelihood for many.

The Attica region, Greece, has undergone major population growth over the past century, without implementing appropriate drainage networks. Flooding in the area is greatly affected by human activities (Diakakis, 2013). High levels of urbanisation in particular can be a major contributor to flood risk (Owusu et al., 2015) and there have been 52 flood events reported in the past 130 years. The Kifisos river has flooded with greater frequency in recent times, reportedly due to unlicensed construction of buildings, levees and bridges along the riverbank and across the flood channels.

2.3 Participation in environmental monitoring

SCENT seeks to tackle the lack of engagement from individuals and groups in influencing environmental policies by engaging people in environmental monitoring through citizen observatories. Another objective is to add to the GEOSS initiative which seeks to increase “understanding of Earth processes and enhances predictive capabilities that underpin sound decision making” (Group on Earth Observations, 2016, p. 5). There is a great opportunity to engage citizens in this sort of work as people are near constantly engaging with online geographic information through platforms such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter (Capineri et al., 2016). In addition, people are voluntarily contributing to these networks often high in quality (COST, 2012), creating further opportunities to exploit, integrate and apply these networks (Capineri et al., 2016).

In particular reference to the Danube Delta, (Bell et al., 2011) suggest that encouraging volunteering within the region may pose a particular challenge because “the memory of state sponsored volunteerism continues to exercise a powerful negative influence on volunteer motivation and recruitment efforts in post-communist countries” (p. 175).

2.3.1 Citizen Science/Observatories

Citizen science is used to broadly define activities which engage the public in in scientific research projects, typically on a voluntary basis with varying degrees of expertise, in collaboration with researchers and scientists (UKEOF, 2016; Van Vliet and Moore, 2016). Citizen observatories (CO) can be viewed as a stream of citizens’ own understanding and interpretation of their environment (Bartonova, 2015) and a complementary activity to professional collection of data (See et al., 2016).

The voluntary nature of participation in CO is often motivated by a desire to be “contributing to the greater good” or “gaining something tangible” (See et al., 2016). The “social experience” of the network is also critical to the success of such observation networks, combined with cognitive and emotional drivers (Bell et al., 2008).

Motivations for participation in CO have been identified by DEFRA (2015) and (Bell et al., 2008) as:

- Altruism – desiring to help wildlife, making a meaningful contribution to science, adding value and helping a particular site, sharing knowledge;
- Skills development – adding skills for personal development and enhancing one’s career;
- Social – engaging with like-minded people for a collective purpose, spending time outdoors and enjoying nature;
- Social desirability – participating because someone else wanted them to;
- Recognition – requiring timely feedback on the usefulness of their work and the impact their own data is having in terms of adding value to the project.

CO can also lead to behaviour change amongst participants who can be empowered to make better choices for themselves and influence their community and policy (Liu et al., 2014), and allow for communication of core concepts of sustainable development in such projects (Chapman, 2015).

COs that acknowledge the power and importance of volunteer motivations so far as including them in their project perform better in terms of enticing and maintain volunteers (Geoghegan et al., 2016). Chapman (2015) also highlighted the importance of design and implementation of citizen observatories in influencing motivation of citizens. They also highlight that such projects should employ mechanisms to motivate and retain participants (Chapman, 2015). Additional motivations for participating can be intrinsic, whereby the participation is inherently valuable and satisfying, or extrinsic, perhaps leading to another benefit in kind e.g. skill development (Geoghegan et al., 2016). Competition has also been employed in digital based CO projects as well as a more general motivation to contribute in a meaningful way to scientific discovery (Geoghegan et al., 2016).

Gamification can be particularly effective in fostering inclusion and a community spirit in projects, as well as being a mechanism for maintaining reputation and ranking amongst members. However, motivation can come under threat if people do not feel able to compete with others in the game (Geoghegan et al., 2016). Emphasis of certain benefits can also be important in recruiting volunteers, for example, skills development. Volunteers can also play a critical role in recruiting other volunteers and disseminating key messages (DEFRA, 2015). Volunteers are more likely to maintain participation when the initial motivations for participating have been fulfilled (UKEOF, 2016) and so opportunities for feedback in which volunteers can identify if their initial motivations have been met are important. The most critical part of continued participation by volunteers was regular communication and feedback from the CO, (Garbarino and Mason, 2016) describe this as “akin to customer service, should there be questions or the need to troubleshoot”.

(Garbarino and Mason, 2016) also comment that citizens need clarity over the scope and limitations of the project and understand the overall objectives of the project. Another challenge for citizen science is being able to recruit participants, which is often contingent on the nature of the project. In addition, if there is low awareness of the issue, this can be a barrier to participation. There can also be issues over the quality of the data collected, particularly as projects are scaled up there is a risk that protocols will be neglected and lower quality data recorded.

2.3.2 Previous EU Projects

Previous European projects have identified various barriers and issues in relation to earth observation (EO) networks. Awareness of these is important for understanding what barriers could exist for citizen involvement in SCENT and the success of the entire project. Firstly, engaging regional stakeholders across the entire network is critical; secondly, addressing the regional requirements for the EO in terms of the user needs; thirdly, ensuring access to data and skills for the EO are easy and free to access; fourthly, building up regional capabilities and skills; and fifthly, building upon synergies with local initiatives (Kontoos, 2016). The projects discussed below received funding from the European Commission under EU FP7.

2.3.2a CITI-SENSE

CITI-SENSE was a citizen observatory project with the purpose of empowering citizens to influence decision making and policy processes in relation to air quality. The project developed, tested, demonstrated and validated community-based environmental monitoring and used novel and innovative EO applications.

(Arpaci et al., 2015) highlight the importance of connections at an individual level with citizens and in CITI-SENSE they established good relationships with local authorities and schools in the pilot programmes. However, poor timing in getting sensors into the public domain and other “technological factors” such as unfamiliarity with the technology may have inhibited engagement. Another weakness that those involved in the project identified was the use of established participatory networks as a means of dissemination, as it made it harder to reach those outside of the networks. The project also struggled in motivating volunteers to install static sensors and convince the volunteers to engage with this new initiative, and that the local authorities would also be proactive in installing static sensors. The process of using already established participatory networks did however lend itself well to further co-operation from local authorities with new projects, but on the other hand this could threaten the longevity of CITI-SENSE if other similar projects are vying for their engagement.

2.3.2b WeSenselt

WeSenselt developed a citizen observatory specifically focused on water and flooding, in which citizens could share collective intelligence about events and places; improve responses during emergencies and improve day to day prevention, protection and preparation for future events; and implement innovative approaches to planning, decision-making and governance (Watson, 2016).

The project identified the key factors in maintaining co-participation of citizens as: “engage citizens in directly interacting with authorities and other stakeholders”; and “provide services for viewing, requesting and feeding back information.” One of their main priorities was to create a “permanent community of contributors sharing useful information” (Mazumdar, 2016) and important consideration was given to cultural variations in approaches to problems; political differences and a “lack of responsibility.” Another important point highlighted was the need for regular maintenance of online portals as a mechanism for maintaining engagement with participants. (Lanfranchi and McCarthy, 2014) also highlighted the importance of “designing a user-centred approach” which requires consultation with the user from the start of the process to understand the reality of people’s involvement in the project. A strong feedback loop from the citizens collecting data to the data users is another critical component (Wehn, 2016).

2.3.2c COBWEB

In a similar vein of CO, COBWEB sought to bring together and empower citizens to contribute data for the purposes of policy formation and governance (COBWEB, 2017). There was a strong focus on keeping the project citizen-centric to ensure information being inputted into local decision making was transparent and credible (Hunt et al., 2015). This type of citizen involvement was also important for local authorities as a means of “monitoring the policies they pursue and assess what is happening on the ground” (Hunt et al., 2015, p. 12). A key theme of the project was that “as long as interaction is kept intuitive, there is potential for use by the public with little or no training” (Davis and Higgins, 2015, p. 92).

2.3.3 Current EU Projects

Under Horizon 2020 funding, there are at least three other CO related projects. The visions of each project are presented below along with any insights they have ascertained through their work conducted to date.

2.3.3a GROW

GROW is a CO for growers, gardens, small and family farmers, and space scientists. It aims to “underpin smart and sustainable custodianship of land and soil, whilst meeting the demands of future food production” (Grow, 2017) and “create a sustainable citizen platform and community to generate, share and utilise information on land, soil and water resource at a resolution hitherto not previously considered” (European Commission, 2016d). The outcome it wishes to achieve is a “hub of open knowledge and data created and maintained by growers that will be valuable to the citizens themselves as well as specialist communities linked through digital and social platforms” (European Commission, 2016d).

2.3.3b LandSense

LandSense has the objective of implementing a citizen observatory that brings together in-situ data for monitoring of land use and providing tools for citizens voices to be heard (LandSense, 2017). It will “deliver concrete, measurable and quality assured ground-based data that will complement existing monitoring systems.” Importantly in this context, the project will utilise numerous methods of citizen empowerment through the LandSense Engagement Platform, i.e. discussion boards, collaboration mapping and events for public consultation (European Commission, 2016e).

2.3.3c Ground Truth 2.0

This project focuses on flora and fauna, water availability and quality, and land and natural resource management (Ground Truth 2.0, 2016). Their methodology aims to bring together the social components of a CO and allowing customisation to be tailored to the anticipated economic and social impacts of the observatory (Ground Truth 2.0, 2016).

2.4 Conclusions

This chapter has presented the background for the need for environmental monitoring based on climate change, the attitudes and behaviours of EU citizens towards the environment and land

resource issues; and then investigated the work to date in the field of citizen observatories. These will form the basis for designing appropriate and high impact incentives in the SCENT project.

The chapter has highlighted the importance of climate change to EU citizens, and that the environment is a concern. However, these attitudes have not changed in recent time. Motivations for engaging in pro-environmental behaviours can vary across individuals, but typically come down to extrinsic and intrinsic factors such as avoidance of guilt or social norms, personal experience and feelings of ownership of the environment. Self-efficacy – the belief that one can make a difference – is also an important factor. However, only 50% have taken some form of action and there is a strong belief in the environment being a shared responsibility. In both countries focused on in this chapter, Greece and Romania, few feel well informed about the environment, but it is a more important issue it would appear to the Greek people than Romanian. There is, however, a low amount of personal responsibility for environmental protection, and an onus on governments to do more to protect the environment. Flooding is an important issue in both regions for the pilot studies, which will be discussed more closely in Chapters 3 and 4 when the primary research methods were employed.

Importantly for the success of SCENT, the motivations for involvement in citizen observatories include factors such as personal skills development, the social aspect of engaging with like-minded people, desire to help the environment, recognition of value, or because someone had asked them to get involved. Communicating with citizen participants and giving feedback on their work was regularly mentioned throughout the literature, and from other EU projects, as key to the success of citizen observatories. Understanding these sorts of behaviours and attitudes of citizens will be of importance to the SCENT project as a whole as we strive to engage citizens in environmental monitoring in their area.

3 Online survey

As part of the quantitative assessment of citizens' attitudes and behaviours towards land-use monitoring and their involvement in SCENT, an online survey was distributed amongst citizens in Romania and Greece. A review of existing literature relating to citizen engagement in environmental monitoring, and in particular flooding, was conducted and informed the questions.

As noted previously, the survey was conducted in conjunction with Task 1.1, details of which can be found in Deliverable 1.1. The online survey was also used as a method of recruiting participants to the focus groups held in the Attica region. Respondents were invited at the end of the survey to sign up for a focus group slot, with an option not to sign up also provided. Further details of the focus groups are given in chapter 4.

As part of the research conducted in Task 1.1, the survey for this task was also distributed amongst groups of citizens in Ireland and the UK. The results from these citizens are also described below and add another helpful level of opinion to the discussion.

3.1 Methods

The survey was developed and distributed to citizens via the online survey platform, Qualtrics. Qualtrics is a highly professional research tool used by leading academic institutions with a professional appearance that allowed for the survey to be branded for the SCENT project in line with the brand strategy presented in D2.1. An example of a page from the survey can be found in Appendix 3. The survey and any corresponding materials were translated by local partners in the Romanian and Greek languages to ensure that the survey was as accessible as possible to citizens.

Random sampling was employed by local partners in the Danube Delta, Romania, Attica region, Greece and to select organisations in Ireland and the UK, who distributed the survey amongst their networks of citizens. There were 179 responses in total to the online survey (Romania: 41 responses; Greek: 94; English: 44).

An outline of the questions asked as part of this survey can be found in Appendix 2.

3.1.1 Data collection protocol

Before completing the online survey, citizens were given an information sheet about SCENT and asked to fill out a consent form. This form followed the informed consent sheet as presented in Deliverable 8.3, with some modifications in presentation made to suit the online display, as presented in Appendix 1. The information collected through the online survey was for the sole purposes of D1.1 and D2.2.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Romania

41 responses were collected from citizens in the Danube Delta. The average respondent was aged 25-34 years (male=51%), finished education when 20 or more years old and was in full time employment.

The most popular activities engaged in by citizens relating to the environment are displayed in *Table 2*. Discussion amongst friends and family is rated as most common, as well as signing petitions. Social media is a popular platform for engaging with environmental issues.

	Activity	Frequency of response
1	Discussed environmental issues with friends/family	38
2	Signed a petition about an environmental issue	34
3	Watched a TV programme specifically concerning the environment	30
4	Posted on social media about the environment	29
=5	Shared your own photos on social media of the environment	24
=5	Attended meetings in your local area about an environmental issue	24
=7	Followed an environmental group on social media	21
=7	Become a member of an environmental group	21
9	Voted for a “green”/an environmental candidate in an election	14
10	Written a letter/lobbied government/Councillors about environmental issues	7

Table 2: Engagement in activities related to the environment (Romania)

61% strongly disagree with the statement “my property has a high risk of flooding”, but when it comes to the likelihood of flooding affecting their livelihood the consensus is less clear, as 46% do believe that flooding is likely to affect their livelihood, whereas others (37%) would tend to disagree with this. The citizens do not believe that the risk of their property being flooded has increased over the past decade (76% disagree). Only 17% would somewhat agree with the statement that they regularly consult flood / river hazard maps in their area. 76% have not been affected by flooding or landslides in their current property. Generally, people feel informed about the flood risks in their area (41% agree, 32% neither agree nor disagree). Only 12% have volunteered to help monitor changes in the environment in their local area. 48% would disagree that their local government are doing all they can to prevent flood events from occurring.

Popular activities that reflect some level of engagement with nature include, but are not limited to: going for walks (80% engage often); reading books on nature (68% engage often); and taking pictures of nature (59% engage often). Exercising outdoors is also a popular activity, but is engaged in less often by citizens. Engaging in the measurement of specific features of fields, rivers, lakes etc. is rarely/never done by 49% of citizens; going fishing is rarely/never done by 73% of citizens. These results are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: How often do you engage in the following activities? (Romania)

Social media and the internet in general are also cited as a popular source for deriving information about flood risks amongst citizens in the Danube Delta. TV is also a common source of information on flood risks. 90% of citizens surveyed own a smartphone and social networks are increasingly popular, 85% of respondents use social media every day. The most popular social network is Facebook, used by 95% of respondents. Taking pictures with a smartphone is also a popular activity, 29% do this each day, and 36% share content online each day.

3.2.2 Greece

94 responses were collected from citizens in the Attica region. The average respondent was aged 35-44 years (male=53%), finished education when 20 or more years old and was in full time employment.

The most popular activities to engage in was watching TV programmes that specifically relate to the environment and discussing environmental issues with friends and family, as displayed in Table 3.

Engagement with government in relation to the environment is less common in terms of voting for “green” candidates, or lobbying.

	Activity	Frequency of response
1	Watched a TV programme specifically concerning the environment	66
2	Discussed environmental issues with friends/family	62
3	Followed an environmental group on social media	42
4	Signed a petition about an environmental issue	41
5	Posted on social media about the environment	34
6	Donated money to an environmental group	32
=7	Become a member of an environmental group	28
=7	Shared your own photos on social media of the environment	28
9	Attended meetings in your local area about an environmental issue	25
10	Voted for a “green”/an environmental candidate in an election	17
11	Written a letter/lobbied government/Councillors about environmental issues	10

Table 3: Engagement in activities related to the environment (Greece)

48% agree with the view that there is a high risk of flooding for their property. Many also consider that flooding is likely to affect their livelihood (43% agree). 44% agree that the risk of their property being flooded has increased over the past decade. 20% would consult flood/river hazard maps on a somewhat regular basis. Only 4% strongly agree that their current property has been affected by flooding and/or landslides. There is no clear consensus on how well informed people are about flood risks in their area (34% agree; 30% neither agree nor disagree; 36% disagree). 20% would agree that they have volunteered to help monitor changes in the environment. There is a general disagreement that the local government are doing all they can to help with preventing flood events from occurring (28% neither agree nor disagree; 60% disagree).

Figure 2: How often do you engage in the following activities? (Greece)

Figure 2 displays the frequency of engagement in various daily activities in which someone may engage with the environment, or observe changes in the environment that may increase the risk of flooding, landslides, etc. The most popular activities are going for walks, exercising and taking pictures of nature. For Greek citizens, going fishing and measuring specific features of fields, rivers, lakes, etc. (e.g. water levels, pH, etc.) are rarely or never engaged in.

Typically, Greek citizens would look for information on flood risks that may affect them on the internet, specifically websites for civil protection and for the meteorological organisation, contact local government and use social media. Social media is very popular and used each day by 71% of respondents.

3.2.3 Other EU countries (Ireland and the UK)

44 responses were collected from citizens in Ireland and the UK. The average respondent was aged 35-44 years (female=61%), finished education when 20 or more years old and was in full time employment.

	Activity	Frequency of response
=1	Discussed environmental issues with friends/family	42
=1	Watched a TV programme specifically concerning the environment	42
3	Read literature on environmental issues	39
4	Voted for a “green”/an environmental candidate in an election	31
5	Signed a petition about an environmental issue	29
6	Followed an environmental group on social media	28
7	Attended meetings in your local area about an environmental issue	21
8	Shared your own photos on social media of the environment	20
9	Posted on social media about the environment	16
10	Donated money to an environmental group	15
11	Become a member of an environmental group	13
12	Written a letter/lobbied government/Councillors about environmental issues	12

Table 4: Engagement in activities related to the environment (Ireland and the UK)

As was found among Romanian and Greek citizens, people will discuss environmental issues with friends and family and watch TV programmes specifically about the environment. Reading literature

is also popular and voting for environmental candidates in elections. Posting on social media about the environment is less commonly engaged in.

In general, respondents disagreed that their home was at a high risk of flooding (77%). Some did agree that flooding was likely to affect their livelihood (25%). 43% strongly disagreed that the risk of their property being flooded had significantly increased over the past decade. 11% agreed with the statement that they regularly consult flood/river hazard maps for their area. 11% had been affected by flooding or landslides in their current property, note that there was no correlation between the respondents who consult flood/river hazard maps and had been affected by flooding. 43% felt well informed about flood risks in their area. Few (11%) had volunteered to monitor changes in the environment. There was a general disagreement that local governments were doing enough to prevent flooding (52% disagree; 23% neither agree nor disagree).

Figure 3: How often do you engage in the following activities? (Ireland and the UK)

Figure 3 shows the popularity of exercising outdoors and going for walks amongst citizens in Ireland and the UK. Involvement in measuring specific features of fields, rivers, lakes, etc. is a much more popular activity to engage with in Ireland and the UK than in Romania and Greece, but still only 16% would be involved in this often.

Typically, people would look on the Office of Public Works website, the national weather service, TV, social media, local county government websites, receive local newsletters/papers, flood maps, department of the environment/agriculture, environmental protection authority, and through word of mouth.

88% of respondents use the internet on their smartphone more than once each day. Social networks are popular – used every day by 61% of respondents. Taking pictures with smartphones is also a common activity, 81% of respondents use their phone to take pictures at least a few times per week. 31% would share content online such as pictures and articles at least once per day.

3.3 Discussion

Amongst all of the citizens surveyed, it is clear that the environment is an important enough issue for them that they discuss it amongst family and friends. Watching TV programmes specifically concerning the environment and signing petitions are also activities citizens will participate in. This information is important because it suggests that citizens do care about the environment enough for it to be discussed amongst themselves, and that TV is a powerful medium for them to engage with environmental issues and a mechanism for shaping attitudes and potential behaviours. Apart from signing petitions, engaging with political activities related to the environment appears less common.

Specifically, in relation to land-use issues such as flooding, Greek citizens perceive their properties to have a higher risk of flooding than Romanian and Irish/British. Few citizens across all countries surveyed have been affected by flooding and/or landslides in their current property.

There is currently a low level of engagement in environmental monitoring activities, and few would regularly consult flood/river hazard maps. This is important for the SCENT project as it seeks to develop a people-centric observation web, whereby citizens carry low-cost sensors for the purpose of monitoring changes in the environment and mould this into a social norm.

There is a recurring theme that citizens view their local governments are not doing all they can to prevent flooding. The SCENT project will tackle this issue by empowering citizens to become the “eyes” of the policy makers.

The SCENT project can also utilize activities that citizens are already frequently engaged in. For example, exercising outdoors and going for walks are common in all countries surveyed. Taking pictures is also a popular activity for citizens to engage in, and with the proliferation of smartphones, it is easier than ever for citizens to take pictures of the environment for the purposes of SCENT.

There is a great deal of commonality in the sources that citizens will consult when it comes to environmental monitoring. These sources can have a powerful impact on citizen attitudes and shaping citizen behaviour and motivating their engagement in projects such as SCENT.

4 Focus groups

For the qualitative assessment of citizens' attitudes and behaviours towards land-use monitoring and their involvement in SCENT, focus groups were held in the pilot regions of the project – the Danube Delta, Romania and Attica region, Greece.

4.1 Methods

Six focus groups lasting 90 minutes each were held for the Danube Delta on Monday 28th and Tuesday 29th November, 2016 at the Danube Delta National Institute, Tulcea, Romania; and for the Attica region on Thursday 1st and Friday 2nd December, 2016 at the National Technical University of Athens, Greece in the same format. Citizen participants were recruited by consortium partners DDNI, SOR, ICCS, ATTICA and HRTA. Details of the participants in each of the focus groups can be found in Appendix 4.

Citizens in the focus groups were given an introduction to the SCENT project and invited to fill out an informed consent form (see Appendix 1) confirming their participation in the project. The discussions within the groups were guided by the discussion outline as presented in Table 5 below.

These questions were created to guide the discussion in determining citizens' current behaviours and attitudes towards engagement with the environment in general as a basis for deeper discussions centred in particular around flooding and changes in land-use. The focus groups were also a time for discussing the SCENT project in more detail with citizens and understanding any barriers to involvement and what mechanisms could motivate citizen engagement in the project. Naturally, the conversations within the focus group flowed into other areas relevant to SCENT but outside the scope of this report, e.g. understanding citizens as user of SCENT and their requirements for the SCENT Toolbox. Findings from these discussions were given to relevant partners to be included in their considerations in the project, e.g. Deliverable 1.1 "SCENT Stakeholder Analysis and End-user requirements".

Environmental attitudes and behaviours

Engagement

- What do you currently do to protect the environment? How do you feel about it?
- Does this have an impact?
- How do you see the role of fellow citizens on the environment?
- What are policy makers doing?

•Concerns

- What changes have you observed in the environment?
- Has your behaviour changed towards the environment?
- Is enough being done to protect the environment?

Flooding and land use change

Past

- What changes have you observed in how land has been used?
- Do you remember any significant flood events?
- Can you recall any changes since your childhood?
- Did these changes/events worry you?
- What lessons could be learned from this?

Present

- How would you describe your current attitudes towards flooding and changes in land use? Why? How are you involved?
- What behaviours have you observed others engaging in? What motivates that behaviour? Are others doing enough?
- What sources of information do you use and trust?
- Do you engage in any monitoring of flooding/changes yourself?
- How active a threat do you consider flooding/changes?

Future

- What do you think the impact of your current behaviour will be?
- How will society’s current activities impact on flooding/land use?
- Are you optimistic or pessimistic about the future and why?
- How can citizens help?
- How could you be involved in Scent?

Table 5: Focus group discussion outline

4.2 Detailed findings

4.2.1 Romania

What do you currently do to protect the environment? How do you feel about it? Does it have an impact? How do you see the role of fellow citizens on the environment? What about the policy makers?

Participants were very passionate about the environment, appreciating “the beauty of nature”. Some were involved in watching and protecting birds and had observed changes in the birds that were coming to the area. These participants also made comment on the reduction of habitats in their area for birds to rest in and blamed a reduction in forestry for this change. One member of this group had even bought a plot of land to plant trees and recreate the natural habitat and attract birds back to the area that had vanished in the wake of deforestation. Others were involved in educating people, through eco-tourism and felt that teaching people about how to care for the environment was impactful. The researchers from the Danube Delta Institute felt that their work had a positive contribution to the environment.

Figure 4: Romanian Focus Group in action

In general, the focus group participants suggested that people in a very general sense simply don't have much interest in the environment. There was concern over behaviours of those who live in on the delta that some of the citizens living there were compounding the environmental issues by leaving trash lying around, throwing it into the water or burning it and creating toxic fumes. Tourists also came under criticism for being a potential pollutant, but some

of the tourist guides revealed ways in which they work to educate the tourists to be responsible patrons of the delta. These tourist guides stated that “we are all citizens and can all make a difference.”

The authorities were perceived to be doing some good things, such as having “environmental guard”, but the area they have to monitor is too great for the number of wardens. The authorities, such as the government, were criticised for encouraging agricultural activities through giving out subsidies across all areas of the country, even in those areas not traditionally used for agriculture. This was mentioned frequently by participants as having a negative impact on the delta, as people change land use to agricultural because of the financial incentive to do so, or at least this was the citizens' perception.

What changes have you observed in the environment? Has your behaviour changed towards the environment? Is enough being done to protect the environment?

The focus group participants recognised that there is “a trace of a human touch” in the delta. Someone also commented on the introduction of monopolistic landowners who controlled the land, and so controlled resources such as the fish available in the delta. Other changes related specifically to flooding and land-use are discussed in the next question.

What changes have you observed in how land has been used? Do you remember any significant flood events? Can you recall any changes since your childhood? Did these changes/events worry you? What lessons could be learned from this?

The participants pointed at two key factors in changes in the Danube Delta. The first: human interventions brought about by the introduction of agriculture and canalization under communism, under which it was proposed that 80% of the land would be transformed into agricultural land. Agriculture is further cited as problematic to the region as chemicals used in those processes can reach bodies of water through leakage and infiltration, affecting the Danube Delta ecosystems. The nature of transport in the delta has also changed and is viewed as potentially having a negative impact as people now use engine boats rather than rowing boats, leading to increased pollution from oil and gas leaks into the water of the delta. The building of homes on areas prone to flooding was also mentioned by some participants, which has led to further building of embankments by the authorities. They would apportion some blame to the authorities for approving the building of these houses, and the house builders for building those flood prone areas and the resultant risk of flooding for citizens who live there.

The second: climatic changes, whereby some citizens held the view that seasonal patterns of rainfall had changed in the region. The focus group highlighted that flooding in the region is not necessarily a bad thing, but has a positive impact on the ecosystems. One participant recalled a particular flood event from his childhood, whilst there was devastation and it was a terrible event, the people were optimistic that it would pass and knew that “a good flooding year will give fish for three years more”.

How would you describe your current attitudes towards flooding and changes in land use? Why? How are you involved? What behaviours have you observed others engaging in? What motivate that behaviour? Are others doing enough? What sources of information do you use and trust? Do you engage in any monitoring of flooding/changes yourself?

The groups suggested that people are concerned only when there is an imminent risk and in that case, they will use their own methods to protect their livelihood. Then, people will get involved in building dykes for example, and reduce the potential impact to themselves and their community. In this case, they are willing to help, but only so far as they have a personal interest in the matter.

The most trustworthy sources were perceived by the groups to be TV, radio and the local authorities. As a source of information, the EU was viewed as too distant to give accurate information, “rara avis” as one participant said. Those who frequently visit the Danube Delta said that local people are one of the best sources and provide information closer to reality. More granular data relating to the delta is harder to come by, with authorities tending to hold this information and only being willing to share it for a price, participants in the focus groups suggested. They suggested that information held by GEOSS was not very timely or accessible.

What do you think the impact of your current behaviour will be? How will society’s current activities impact on flooding/land use? Are you optimistic or pessimistic about the future and why? How can citizens help? How could you be involved in SCENT?

Some members of the focus groups wish for the land to be restored to its previous status, e.g. reforesting agricultural fodder or restoring wetlands. Some also suggested that many people simply do not care, and so intrinsic motivators will not be effective in motivating citizens to action. They

suggest that for SCENT to have an impact, citizens will require lots of information and be communicated with through personal connections, not just the media. Some participants highlighted the potential impact of teachers on the younger generation as a means for engagement in SCENT. Through the school setting, people are hearing and acting on messages about the environment from what they perceive to be a trustworthy source and are more likely to be motivated to positive action. Further discussion also highlighted the potential impact of role-models such as sportspeople, and an example was given of a Romanian Olympian who has motivated many to take up water sports in the wake of his success.

4.2.2 Greece

What do you currently do to protect the environment? How do you feel about it? Does it have an impact? How do you see the role of fellow citizens in the environment? What are policy makers doing?

Participants in the focus groups engaged in recycling, using “eco-driving” settings in cars, using renewable energy sources, and participating in outdoor pursuits such as canoeing. One participant stated that “we are all full of good intentions,” but recognised that environmental consciousness in Greece was at a low level and carried an idea that “we have abandoned nature and become urban creatures”. The environment dropped in priority in the wake of the financial crisis and there is an expectation on policy makers to do something. Some perceived that local governments were not doing enough, particularly in relation to recycling. In addition, if there was no immediate benefit, then people were unlikely to engage. In a similar vein, people do not consider the future costs, for example of dumping rubbish in the river upstream. They also saw power in networks, knowledge based and social, in passing on messages and conveying good examples of behaviour, making private environmental behaviours public. Some also suggested that they were not doing enough when it came to the preservation of river banks, which has been a particular issue along the Kifisos river. One participant suggested that authorities should take more drastic action against illegal building along the river bank.

What changes have you observed in the environment? Has your behaviour changed towards the environment? Is enough being done to protect the environment? What changes have you observed in how land has been used? Do you remember any significant flood events? Can you recall any changes since your childhood? Did these changes/events worry you? What lessons could be learned from this?

Members of these focus groups highlighted that climate phenomena have become stronger, “like nothing we’ve seen in the past”, with more intense rainfall, bigger disasters, greater periods of drought. In addition, human generated factors have had a profound impact, for example through building on the natural river bank of the Kifisos river, and through deforestation which has occurred upstream. Deforestation has been caused both by people cutting down trees, and also through intense wildfires, and reforestation has not yet occurred. They suggest that it is “a matter of time” before the next flood event occurs.

Citizens in the focus groups suggested some lessons that can be learned from other projects, for example, they consider that citizens often don’t join projects if they can’t help sufficiently and their

contribution must make a significant impact. The groups believed that information about the environment was widely available, but still people would not make use of it.

Thanking people straight away for their participation can act as an important motivator, helping people to foster an attitude of contributing to something bigger and to their community.

How would you describe your current attitudes towards flooding and changes in land use? Why? How are you involved? What behaviours have you observed others engaging in? What motivates that behaviour? Are others doing enough? What sources of information do you use and trust? Do you engage in any monitoring of flooding/changes yourself?

Some members of the focus group had participated in flood rescues in 2000 and 2002, when there had been very intense weather phenomena in which significant material damage was incurred by those affected. Flooding is a disastrous phenomenon, but rare and there is less education than other phenomena such as fires and earthquakes. Citizens can get help in flood events more easily than earthquakes, for example, but still don't know how to protect themselves from flooding. Greater education is required, perhaps through gaming or similar. Many people believe their home will not flood (e.g. they live on a hill), and so it does not concern them. Floods are more forecastable and can be mapped more easily than earthquakes, for example, and much more localised. As the river banks change though, the nature of the risks changes which people need to be made aware of.

Along the Kifisos river, there are many different neighbourhoods, each with different demographic profiles and each neighbourhood will be impacted differently. As such, people don't have a connection with the river, it is not a "live" river but is seen as a source of problems which people "only remember when it is raining". One participant suggested creating a connection between the people and the river, which would increase the care and interest they take it in.

There was a view that people don't take initiative to change things, to put the information they know of climate change, of flood events, of flood prevention and protection into action. They need to change their attitudes individually and collectively. Someone also mooted the idea that citizens do not care about other people or pay attention to other communities. Additional information to citizens was suggested as a solution to this to boost awareness and motivate participation.

Regarding sources of information, the groups suggested that people would use weather apps on smartphones or they would need to search for information about the river. The use of the word "search" would suggest that this information is not widely known and some effort is required to discover it.

What do you think the impact of your current behaviour will be? How will society's current activities impact on flooding/land use? Are you optimistic or pessimistic about the future and why? How can citizens help? How could you be involved in SCENT?

Figure 5: Greek Focus Group in action

For engaging citizens in SCENT, the group suggested that we should start

by targeting those living in flood prone areas, in particular those who have been affected already. Once one group have been mobilised, that will spur others on to further engagement. However, some participants also held the view that citizens are not very interested in protecting the environment.

Various incentive mechanisms were suggested such as free apps, creating contests and competition between citizens, motivating through ranking, giving instant feedback to users of SCENT, fostering shared experiences between users, giving “moral rewards” and belief that they are contributing to something useful and powerful, activating media was also highlighted as important and engaging people in learning about the Kifisos river. The focus groups identified some groups who could also be targeted for involvement in SCENT: hikers, bikers, cyclists, schools and volunteer groups.

4.3 Discussion

In both regions, the citizens have observed changes in the environment, in particular relation to land use which has contributed to changes in flooding behaviour. These have not been positive changes in either case. However, the attitudes towards flooding are an important point of difference between the two regions. In the Danube Delta, flooding is associated with life and biodiversity, it keeps the life cycle going. In contrast, in Attica region, the Kifisos river is associated with destruction and disruption.

In both regions, they feel that their governments are doing something in terms of pursuing environmental protection, but it is still not enough. This correlates with the findings of chapter 3. In addition, in both regions, citizens are only concerned with getting involved in the environment when there is an imminent, material threat to their wellbeing. It was suggested by study participants that they would require some sort of incentive for participation. One sort of incentive suggested was the gamification of the app to create a competition between participants and utilising personal connections between participants.

5 Conclusions

The objective of this Research Report has been to detail the current attitude and behaviours of citizens in relation to land resource management issues. In conclusion, climate change is an important concern to EU citizens. Flooding in particular affects the lives of citizens in Romania and Greece, but for different reasons. For those based in the Danube Delta, flooding is a positive part of the water cycle and promotes a vibrant ecology in the area. The Danube Delta is a source of life for many, but has been impacted upon by human interventions, namely the development of agriculture. For citizens, local to the Kifisos river, it was suggested that people only remember it exists when it is raining and causes problems such as flooding businesses and homes. Many would trace the increase in flood events along the Kifisos to deforestation in the mountains above Athens, and inappropriate building along the river bank.

Bearing in mind the various backgrounds of citizens in these pilot regions, we can appreciate that citizens will get involved in citizen observatories for many different reasons. It is also important to maintain citizens' interest when they are involved in the CO, which can be facilitated to by regular feedback on the value of the work they are contributing. The research also highlighted the importance of making SCENT something that citizens can easily engage with, such as working through already established networks such as cycling clubs or school groups, and incorporating the use of SCENT into activities that citizens are already participating in, such as going for walks in nature, and taking sharing pictures.

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Appendices

A 1 Informed consent forms

For the needs of Task 2.2 and the current deliverable, there was essentially one consent form, provided in two different formats; one handed over to participants of the focus groups and to people interviewed or e-mailed in order to fill in the questionnaires and one appended to the beginning of the online surveys which followed a simpler approach, where the participants were asked to click if they agree with the various statements. Nevertheless, the content in both formats is the same and is provided below. One should note that the consent forms were translated in Greek and Romanian language so that there is no language barrier for the participants.

Informed consent form SCENT project

You are being asked to participate in a research study for the SCENT project. Participation is completely voluntary. Please read the information about the project, its aims, and the gathering of user needs in the SCENT Content Sheet and ask questions about anything that you do not understand.

I, the undersigned, confirm that (please tick box as appropriate):

1.	I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the SCENT Content Sheet.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and my participation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	I voluntarily agree to participate in the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	I understand I can withdraw myself and my data from the project at any time without giving reasons and that I will not be penalised for withdrawing nor will I be questioned on why I have withdrawn.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The procedures regarding confidentiality have been clearly explained (in this case anonymisation of data) to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	If applicable, separate terms of consent for interviews, audio, video or other forms of data collection have been explained and provided to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
7.	The use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving has been explained to me. I understand that data will either be destroyed or reused at the end of the research.	<input type="checkbox"/>
8.	I understand that other researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the data and if they agree to the terms I have specified in this form.	<input type="checkbox"/>
9.	Select only one of the following:	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would like my name used and understand what I have said or written as part of this study will be used in reports, publications and other research outputs so that anything I have contributed to this project can be recognised. • I do not want my name used in this project. 	<input type="checkbox"/>
10.	I, along with the Researcher, agree to sign and date this informed consent form.	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Participant:

Name of Participant	Signature	Date

SCENT:

Name of SCENT partner	Signature	Date

Accompanying this form, the participants were handed over a content sheet of the project, which is provided below (translated into their native language):

“We are carrying out a research survey and we would like you to take part. This research is being carried out as part an EU-funded project called SCENT. The aim of the project is to engage citizens, such as yourself, in actively participating in environmental monitoring in your local area.

The particular focus of this research project is on flooding, and the management and prevention of flooding in your local area. We firmly believe the active participation of local citizens will help to reduce the serious damage and great inconvenience caused by flood events in your area and influence environmental policy.

Technologies such as games, cheap and portable sensors attached to your smartphone and even your smartphone camera will help you to take photographs and other environmental parameters from your local environment. Then, this information will be used to improve current maps and make flooding prediction models more accurate. You will also be able to make local and national policy recommendations based on the conclusions of the research with regards to environmental protection.

This survey aims to understand your opinions on being engaged in the project and the impact that flood events have had on you and your local area. In addition, it asks what you would require from the project to enable you to monitor environmental changes in your area.

Thank you for your participation and support of this project.”

Please read the information below carefully.

We are carrying out a research survey and we would like you to take part. This research is being carried out as part of an EU-funded project called SCENT. The aim of the project is to engage citizens, such as yourself, in actively participating in environmental monitoring in your local area.

The particular focus of this research project is on flooding, and the management and prevention of flooding in your local area. We firmly believe the active participation of local citizens will help to reduce the serious damage and great inconvenience caused by flood events and influence environmental policy. Pilot studies of SCENT will be carried out in the rural case of the Danube Delta, Romania, and in the urban case of the Kifisos River.

Technologies such as games, cheap and portable sensors attached to smartphones and even smartphone cameras will help to take photographs and other environmental parameters from the local environment. Then, this information will be used to improve current maps and make flooding prediction models more accurate. Through this, individuals will be able to make local and national policy recommendations based on the conclusions of the research with regards to environmental protection.

This survey aims to understand your opinions on being engaged in the project and the impact that flood events have had on you and your local area. In addition, it asks what you would require from the project to enable you to monitor environmental changes in your area.

Your input will be of immense value in understanding how SCENT could have an impact outside of Romania and Greece.

Thank you for your participation and support of this project.

You are being asked to participate in a research study for the SCENT project. Participation is completely voluntary.

If you have any questions about anything you have read, please contact Amy Hume, amy@carrcommunications.ie

If you are happy to proceed, please read the information below and indicate your agreement by selecting "I agree" below.

1. I have read and understood the information about the project as presented above.
2. I voluntarily agree to participate in the project
3. I understand I can withdraw myself and my data from the project at any time without giving reasons and that I will not be penalized for withdrawing nor will I be questioned on why I have withdrawn.
4. The procedures regarding confidentiality have been clearly explained (in this case anonymization of data) to me.
5. The use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving has been explained to me. I understand that data will either be destroyed or reused at the end of the research.
6. I understand that other researchers will have access to this data only if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the data and if they agree to the terms I have specified in this form.

By selecting "I agree", you confirm that you have read all the information given on this page and give your informed consent to participate in this research study for the SCENT project.

I agree

I do not agree

A 2 Online survey

The online survey comprised of two parts: one which was related to gathering input from the citizen/user needs regarding SCENT innovations and components as part of Task 1.1 and, thus, was presented in Deliverable 1.1 SCENT Stakeholder Analysis and End-user requirements, and one that is mostly relevant to the current citizen attitudes towards environmental issues and their contribution to them which is relevant to this task; the latter is shown in what follows:

Q3.1 Have you ever engaged in any of the following related to the environment?

Please tick all that apply.

- Posted on social media about environmental issues (1)
- Shared your own photos on social media of the environment (2)
- Followed environmental groups on social media (3)
- Become a member of an environmental group (4)
- Discussed environmental issues with friends/family (5)
- Read literature on environmental issues (6)
- Watched a TV programme specifically concerning the environment (7)
- Signed a petition about an environmental issue (8)
- Voted for a 'green'/environmental candidate in an election (9)
- Donated money to an environmental group (10)
- Written a letter/lobbied government/Councillors about environmental issues (11)
- Attended meetings in local area about an environmental issue (12)

Q3.2 Please indicate your agreement with the following statements.

	Strongly agree (1)	Somewhat agree (2)	Neither agree nor disagree (3)	Somewhat disagree (4)	Strongly disagree (5)
My property has a high risk of flooding (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Flooding is likely to affect my livelihood (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The risk of my property being flooded has significantly increased over the past decade (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I regularly consult flood/river hazard maps in my area (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have been affected by flooding and/or landslides in my current property (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am well informed about flood risks in my area (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have volunteered to help monitor changes in the environment in my area (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My local government are doing all they can to prevent flood events from occurring (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q3.3 How often do you engage in the following activities?

	Often (1)	Sometimes (2)	Occasionally (3)	Rarely (4)	Not at all (5)
Read books on nature (plants, animals, etc.) (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Take pictures of nature (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Go for walks (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Measure specific features of fields, rivers, lakes, etc. (e.g. water levels, pH, etc.) (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Go fishing (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Exercise outdoors (6)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q3.4 Where do you look for information on flood risks that could affect you?

Demographics

Q9.1 Please indicate which age category you belong to.

- Under 18 (1)
- 18 - 24 (2)
- 25 - 34 (3)
- 35 - 44 (4)
- 45 - 54 (5)
- 55 - 64 (6)
- 65 - 74 (7)
- 75 - 84 (8)
- 85 or older (9)
- Prefer not to say (10)

Q9.2 Please indicate your gender

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Other (3)
- Prefer not to say (4)

Q9.3 Your town / city, county, country

Q9.4 Please indicate your employment status

- Employed full time (1)
- Employed part time (2)
- Unemployed looking for work (3)
- Unemployed not looking for work (4)
- Retired (5)
- Student (6)
- Disabled (7)

Display This Question:

If Please indicate your employment status Employed full time Is Selected
And Please indicate your employment status Employed part time Is Selected
And Please indicate your employment status Retired Is Selected

Q9.5 What is or was your occupation?

Q9.6 Which best describes your property ownership status?

- Own outright (1)
- Own with a mortgage (2)
- Rental (5)
- Living with family (6)
- Other (7)

Q9.7 Please indicate what age you finished your education.

- 15 years old or less (1)
- 16-19 years old (2)
- 20 or more years old (3)
- Still in education (4)

A 3 Online Survey screenshots

Romanian citizen survey

The screenshot shows a survey page for the SCENT project in Romanian. At the top right is the SCENT logo. Below it is a language dropdown menu set to 'Română'. The main text explains the survey's purpose: to study flood risks and citizen attitudes. It details the SCENT project's goals, including data collection via smartphones and the use of maps. A list of five terms and conditions is provided at the bottom, covering consent, voluntariness, and data handling.

Va rugam sa cititi cu atentie informatiile de mai jos.

In vederea indeplinirii obiectivelor studiului de cercetare privind riscul la inundatii, gestionarea si prevenirea acestora, va rugam sa ne sprijiniti prin completarea chestionarului urmatoar. Avem certitudinea ca participarea activă a cetățenilor la nivel local va contribui la reducerea daunelor grave și a neplăcerilor cauzate de inundații în zona dumneavoastră și ca exprimarea directă a opiniei dvs poate influența politica de mediu.

SCENT, este un proiect european, finanțat prin Programul de cercetare și inovare Orizont 2020 al Uniunii Europene al carui scop este de a angaja cetățeni, ca dumneavoastra, pentru a participa activ la monitorizarea mediului din zona locală. Prin utilizarea unor instrumente tehnologice, cum ar fi jocurile, senzori portabili atașati la telefonul mobil (smartphone) și chiar camera foto a smartphone-ului veți putea ajuta la colectarea datelor din teren prin realizarea de fotografii precum și colectarea altor parametri de mediu din mediul local. Ulterior, aceste informații vor fi folosite la îmbunătățirea hărților actuale și realizarea unor modele de inundații cu predicție mai precisă. Veți avea de asemenea, posibilitatea de a face recomandări politice locale și naționale, pe baza concluziilor cercetării în ceea ce privește protecția mediului.

Acest sondaj are ca scop înțelegerea opiniilor dvs. și impactul pe care inundațiile le-au avut pentru dvs și zona locală. În plus, de ce anume are nevoie proiectul pentru a vă permite monitorizarea schimbărilor de mediu în zona dumneavoastră

Va mulțumim pentru participare și pentru sprijinul acordat proiectului.

Vi se cere să participe la un studiu de cercetare pentru proiectul SCENT. Participarea este complet voluntară.

Dacă aveți întrebări în legatură cu ce ați citit, vă rugăm să contactați Iulian Nichersu (iulian.nichersu@ddmi.ro)

Dacă sunteți de acord să continuați, vă rugăm să citiți informațiile de mai jos și indicați acordul selectând: "Sunt de acord" de mai jos.

1. Am citit și am înțeles informațiile despre proiect prezentate mai sus.
2. Sunt de acord în mod benevol să particip la proiect.
3. Înțeleg că pot să mă retrag din proiect, în orice moment, fără a motiva, și că nu voi fi penalizat pentru retragere și nici nu voi fi chestionat asupra motivului pentru care m-am retras
4. Procedurile referitoare la confidențialitate mi-au fost explicate în mod clar (fără a ascunde date).
5. Mi s-a explicat modul de folosire al datelor în cercetare, publicatii, schimb și arhivare. Am înțeles ca datele vor fi distruse

Greek citizen survey

Αγαπητή/έ,

Πραγματοποιούμε μία έρευνα στα πλαίσια του ευρωπαϊκά χρηματοδοτούμενου ερευνητικού έργου SCENT στην οποία θα θέλαμε να συμμετάσχετε. Το συγκεκριμένο επιστημονικό έργο εστιάζει στη διαχείριση και πρόληψη των πλημμυρών στην περιοχή σας. Αποτελεί πεποίθησή μας ότι η ενεργή συμμετοχή των πολιτών της περιοχής μπορεί να συμβάλει στη μείωση των σημαντικών επιπτώσεων και της μεγάλης ταλαιπωρίας που προκαλούνται από πλημμυρικά επεισόδια στην περιοχή σας και να επηρεάσει την περιβαλλοντική πολιτική των αρμοδίων αρχών.

Σκοπός του έργου είναι να προσελκύσει πολίτες, όπως εσάς, οι οποίοι θα συμμετάσχουν ενεργά στην περιβαλλοντική παρακολούθηση της περιοχής τους. Τεχνολογίες όπως ψηφιακά παιχνίδια, φορητοί αισθητήρες χαμηλού κόστους, συνδεδεμένοι με το smartphone σας, ακόμα και η ίδια η κάμερα της συσκευής σας, θα βοηθήσουν να βγάζετε φωτογραφίες και να συλλέξετε πληροφορίες για τις περιβαλλοντικές παραμέτρους της περιοχής σας. Στη συνέχεια, αυτές οι πληροφορίες θα χρησιμοποιηθούν από τους αρμοδίους για τη βελτίωση των υφιστάμενων χαρτών και για την ενίσχυση της ακρίβειας των μοντέλων πρόβλεψης πλημμυρών. Θα έχετε, επίσης, τη δυνατότητα να συνδράμετε στη διαμόρφωση προτάσεων τοπικής και εθνικής πολιτικής για την προστασία του περιβάλλοντος, βάσει των συμπερασμάτων της έρευνας.

Η έρευνα στοχεύει στην κατανόηση των απόψεών σας για την πιθανή εμπλοκή σας στο έργο και για τον αντίκτυπο των πλημμυρικών φαινομένων σε εσάς και στην περιοχή σας. Επιπλέον, θα διερευνηθούν οι απαιτήσεις σας από το έργο ώστε να έχετε τη δυνατότητα να παρακολουθείτε τις περιβαλλοντικές μεταβολές στην περιοχή σας.

Σας ευχαριστούμε για την υποστήριξή σας και το χρόνο σας.

Καλείστε να συμμετάσχετε σε μια έρευνα για το ευρωπαϊκό έργο SCENT. Η συμμετοχή είναι εθελοντική. Αν έχετε οποιαδήποτε ερώτηση σχετικά με αυτά που θα διαβάσετε, παρακαλώ επικοινωνήστε με την κα Δήμητρα Αλέξοπούλου, Περιφέρεια Αττικής, Δ/ση Αναπτυξιακού Προγ/σμου, Τμήμα Εφαρμογής Προγ/των & Έργων, τηλ: 2132065221, email: dalexopoulou@patt.gov.gr

Αν είστε διατεθειμένοι να προχωρήσετε με την έρευνα, παρακαλώ διαβάστε τις παρακάτω πληροφορίες και σημειώστε την συγκατάθεσή σας επιλέγοντας το 'Σύμφωνο'.

Έχω διαβάσει και κατανοώ τις πληροφορίες για το έργο, σύμφωνα με τη συνημμένη περιγραφή του έργου.

Δέχομαι εθελοντικά να συμμετάσχω στο έργο.

A 4 Participant Lists in Focus Groups

Participant Lists in Danube Delta

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under GA no 688930

DDNI TULCEA

WP 2 - Focus Group B + Group C : 14:00 - 17:30

CR.	NAME / PRENUM	INSTRUMENTE	TELEFON	E-MAIL	SEMNAVREAN
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7	SEBASTIEN	MAMI	0795520606	sebastien.sela@iqm.ro	
8	AMY NUME	CRK			
9	L. Henriksson Linda	CRK			
10	George Athanasios	ICCS			
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17	DOROSEKA HEKHAIDRU	DDNI	0747334705	doroseka.hekhaidru@iqm.ro	
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19	MAGIMON MIHAEL	DDNI		mihaimon@iqm.ro	

Participant Lists in Attica

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Διημερίδα και Εστιασμένες Ομάδες Συζήτησης στο πλαίσιο του Έργου SCENT

“Οι πολίτες στο επίκεντρο: Τα παρατηρήσιμα πολιτών και πώς μπορούν να συνεισφέρουν στην καλύτερη διαχείριση και πρόβλεψη των πλημμυρικών φαινομένων”

1 & 2 Δεκεμβρίου, 2016 | Αθήνα

α/α	ΟΝΟΜΑΤΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ	ΕΤΟΙΜΕΙΑ ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑΣ	ΥΠΟΓΡΑΦΗ	ΟΜΑΔΑ
1	ΑΔΑΜ ΣΟΦΙΑ	sophia.adam@iccs.gr		Γ
2	ΑΓΑΝΑΣΙΟΥ ΓΙΩΡΓΟΣ			
3	ΓΕΩΡΓΙΟΥ ΧΑΡΗΣ	Xgeorgio@di.koa.gr (ΕΟΔΑ)		Γ
4	ΚΑΡΑΪΣΤΑΝΙΔΗΣ ΓΙΑΝΝΗΣ			Γ
5	KESSERLING EVA			
6	ΚΟΥΝΗΣ ΓΙΑΝΝΗΣ	Kounis@isee.org		Δ
7	ΚΩΣΤΑΚΗΣ ΧΡΗΣΤΟΣ			

8	ΝΟΥΤΙΟΣ ΚΩΣΤΑΣ	Klouros @ iccs. gr		Γ
9	ΑΥΤΡΙΒΗΣ ΠΑΝΑΓΙΩΤΗΣ	panagiotis.kytrivis@iccs.gr		Δ
10	ΜΙΛΚΗ ΑΝΑΣΤΑΣΙΑ - ΙΩΑΝΝΑ	mily@noemail.com coSA.		Ε
11	ΜΠΑΡΟΥΧΑΣ ΠΑΝΤΕΛΗΣ			
12	ΝΟΥΣΑ ΒΑΣΙΛΙΚΗ	coSA		Δ
13	ΠΑΠΑΓΕΩΡΓΙΟΥ ΑΝΔΡΕΑΣ			
14	ΧΟΥΜΗ ΚΩΝΣΤΑΝΤΙΝΑ			
15	CAUCHI ERIC	SEA@Seability.eu		Α
16	ΑΥΚΟΙ ΓΕΡΑΣΙΜΟΣ	Michyias 210 9 74609 gr		Γ
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18	ΜΠΟΤΣΙΣ ΑΘΑΝΑΣΙΟΣ	athm.botsis@guwil.ch		Γ
19	ΒΑΣΙΛΗΣ ΠΑΡΑΣΚΕΥΟΝΟΠΟΥΛΟΣ			Γ
21	ΑΣΑΝΙΣΤΡΑΚΗΣ ΖΑΧΑΡΙΑΣ	coSA		Γ

22	Χρυσή Παναγιώτα	Χρυσή Παναγιώτα	chricha1@di.voc.gr		Δ
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28	Εσδωγός Ευδοκία	Εσδωγός Ευδοκία			
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32	Αννα Αποστολάκη	Αννα Αποστολάκη	anna.apostolaki@iccs.gr		Ε
33	Ιλίσια Νικηφόρου	Ιλίσια Νικηφόρου	ilisia.nikiforos@bki.ro		Ε
34	Ευγενία Πασα	Ευγενία Πασα	eugenia.marin@dduika		Ε
35	Αντζουλα Χολεροπούλου	Αντζουλα Χολεροπούλου	dimi.christo@gmail.com		Ε

A 5 Agenda for Focus Groups

Focus Groups in Attica

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Agenda

SCENT project Workshop and Focus Group Discussions

“People at the Centre: The citizens’ observatories and how they can contribute to better management and forecasting of flood events”

December 1 & 2, 2016 || Athens, Greece

(Venue: Teleconference room, NTUA Central Library, 9 Iroon Polytechniou Street, Zografou Campus, 15773)

Thursday, 1 December 2016	
13:00- 14:00	Welcome & Lunch
14:00 – 15:30	Focus Group C Introduction to SCENT (5') Citizens’ and volunteers’ attitude and views regarding their role in monitoring environmental events (85')
15:30 - 16:00	Coffee break
16:00 – 17:30	Focus Group D Introduction to SCENT (5') Citizens’ and volunteers’ attitude and views regarding their role in monitoring environmental events (85')
Friday, 2 December 2016	
12:30- 13:30	Welcome & Lunch
13:30 – 15:00	Focus Group E Introduction to SCENT (5') Citizens’ and volunteers’ attitude and views regarding their role in monitoring environmental events (85')